

WHITE PAPER – High Energy Astrophysics and Cosmology

The Cherenkov Telescope Array (CTA)

Thematic Areas:

Formation and Evolution of Compact Objects

Cosmology and Fundamental Physics

Stars and Stellar Evolution

Galaxy Evolution

Astroparticles

Multi-Messenger Astronomy and Astrophysics

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On behalf of the CTA Consortium, <https://www.cta-observatory.org/about/cta-consortium/Astro2020> White Paper: The Cherenkov Telescope Array (CTA)

1. Introduction

To advance the state of the art in very-high-energy (VHE) γ -ray astrophysics, an international consortium of 1500 scientists from 31 countries (including Brazil) has converged on the concept of the Cherenkov Telescope Array (CTA) [1]. CTA will consist of two large arrays of imaging atmospheric-Cherenkov telescopes (IACTs), see Figure 1, using techniques to detect VHE γ -rays. These VHE γ -rays are observed via the Cherenkov light produced in particle cascades (showers) generated when they interact in the Earth's atmosphere. A key step in CTA, aside from technological improvements with regard to current IACT observatories and an increase in telescope quantity, is the use of different-sized IACTs to cost-effectively specialize on different parts of the CTA energy regime (20 GeV – 300 TeV). CTA is envisioned as an open observatory (i.e. full community access to investor countries), and will provide full-sky coverage via locations in both the Northern and Southern Hemispheres. High-level CTA data will be available on a public archive after a proprietary period of typically one year. CTA will be the world's largest and most-sensitive γ -ray observatory.

The CTA Science scope is very broad, and will allow to achieve a knowledge of the non-thermal universe in the high energies never reached, with significant contributions to Cosmology, Astrophysics, and Astro-Particle Physics, in an intense synergy between these areas. CTA and its technological capabilities are expected to be unsurpassed in the gamma ray range for at least the next 30 years. CTA will investigate the physical conditions of cosmic particle accelerators (cosmic rays) such as black holes, pulsars, supernovae, and gamma ray bursts; the composition and origin of dark matter; the cosmic magnetic fields; and the violation of the constancy of the speed of light.

Participation of CTA in Brazil started in 2010, when a group of researchers (Vitor de Souza (IFSC-USP), Elisabete M. de Gouveia Dal Pino (IAG-USP), and Ulisses Barres de Almeida (CBPF) officially joined the collaboration. After that, three CTA-BR Parties were formed led by these researchers, and each one were granted funding for helping, within international efforts, the development of the three-different size telescopes of CTA: the Small Size telescopes (SSTs, coordinated by E. M. de Gouveia Dal Pino, IAG-USP), the Middle Size Telescopes (MSTs, coordinated by V. de Souza, IFSC-USP), and the Large Size Telescopes (LSTs, coordinated by U. B. de Almeida, CBPF). So far, the first two parties obtained funding from FAPESP (12.200.000,00 REAIS for SSTs, and 1.800.000,00 REAIS for MSTs), and the last one, from FAPERJ (100.000,00 REAIS for LSTs). New actions for raising more funding for the continuation of the CTA construction are being taken (Sections 4, 5 and 7).

CTA Consortium counts with the participants of all the existing major IACT instruments Worldwide. They are now all working together towards CTA's implementation. CTA is also the major VHE particle astrophysics Project in USA and Europe where it was

included in the 2008 Roadmap of the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) and was designated as an ESFRI Landmark in 2018. It is listed as one of the Magnificent Seven projects comprising the European strategy for astroparticle physics published by ASPERA, and was highly ranked in the strategic plan for European astronomy of ASTRONET. In the U.S., the HEPAP P5 sub-panel review of projects in particle physics noted the unique capabilities of CTA for the detection of dark matter and recommended participation in CTA as a multidisciplinary project.

Figure 1: Artist's concept of the Cherenkov Telescope Array southern site, using engineering drawings of the individual telescopes. Four large-sized telescopes (LSTs) in the center are surrounded by arrays of medium-sized and small-sized telescopes, MSTs and SSTs, respectively.

The transformational capabilities of CTA require an observatory that is in the large ground-based project class, but as a multi-national project, no single nation needs to bear even the majority of the cost. Thus a significant and continuous Brazilian support for CTA construction and operations, at the level of a mid-scale project, would give all Brazilian scientists access to the observatory.

The contents of this white paper draw extensively from the recently completed volume Science with the Cherenkov Telescope Array [2] written by the CTA Consortium.

2. Key Science Goals and Objectives

Ground-based γ -ray astronomy is a young field with enormous scientific potential. The possibility of astrophysical measurements at tera-electronvolt (TeV) energies was demonstrated in 1989 with the detection of a clear signal from the Crab Nebula above 1 TeV with the Whipple 10m IACT [3]. Since then, the instrumentation for, and techniques of, astronomy with IACTs have evolved to the extent that a flourishing new scientific discipline has been established, with the detection of more than 200 sources

and a major impact in astrophysics and more widely in physics. The current major arrays of IACTs: H.E.S.S., MAGIC, and VERITAS, have demonstrated the huge physics potential at these energies as well as the maturity of the detection technique. Many astrophysical source classes have been established, some with many well-studied individual objects, but there are indications that the known sources represent the tip of the iceberg in terms of both individual objects and source classes. CTA will transform our understanding of the high-energy universe and will explore questions in physics of fundamental importance. As a key member of the suite of new and upcoming major astroparticle physics experiments and observatories, CTA will exploit synergies with gravitational wave and neutrino observatories as well as with classical photon observatories. CTA will address a wide range of major questions in and beyond astrophysics, which can be grouped into three broad themes as indicated [2]:

Theme 1: Understanding the Origin and Role of Relativistic Cosmic Particles. The existence of highly energetic cosmic particles has been known for more than a century. CTA observations will contribute providing answers to basic questions such as:

- What are the sites of high-energy particle acceleration in the universe?
- What are the mechanisms for cosmic particle acceleration?
- What role do accelerated particles play in feedback on star formation and galaxy evolution?

Theme 2: Probing Extreme Environments. VHE γ -rays can be used to explore environments of extreme energy density, as well as to probe another type of extreme environment, the cosmic voids that exist in the space between galaxies. Specific questions concern:

- What physical processes are at work close to neutron stars and black holes?
- What are the characteristics of relativistic jets, winds and explosions?
- How intense are radiation fields and magnetic fields in cosmic voids, and how do these evolve over cosmic time?

Theme 3: Exploring Frontiers in Physics. VHE γ -rays also allow us to explore questions related to fundamental physics, reaching far beyond astrophysics. Topics addressed include:

- What is the nature of dark matter? How is it distributed?
- Are there quantum gravitational effects on photon propagation?
- Do axion-like particles exist?

The CTA Consortium (see Sec. 5) has prepared a proposal for a Core Program of highly motivated observations to address these science themes. The program, encompassing approximately 40% of the available observing time over the first ten years of CTA operation, is made up of individual Key Science Projects (KSPs). The science cases have been prepared over several years by the CTA Consortium, with community input gathered via a series of workshops connecting CTA to neighboring communities. A major element of the program is the search for dark matter via the annihilation signature of weakly interacting massive particles (WIMPs). The strategy for dark matter detection places the expected cross-section for a thermal relic within reach of CTA for a wide range of WIMP masses from ~ 200 GeV to 20 TeV.

This makes CTA extremely complementary to other approaches, such as high-energy particle collider and direct-detection experiments. CTA will also conduct a census of particle acceleration over a wide range of astrophysical objects, with quarter-sky extragalactic, full-plane Galactic and Large Magellanic Cloud surveys planned (see Fig. 2). Additional KSPs are focused on transients, acceleration up to PeV energies in our own Galaxy, active galactic nuclei, star-forming systems on a wide range of scales, and the Perseus cluster of galaxies. All provide high-level data products which will benefit a wide community, and together they will provide a long-lasting legacy for CTA.

Figure 2: Top: simulated CTA image of the Galactic plane for the inner region, $-80^\circ < l < 80^\circ$, adopting the proposed Galactic Plane Survey Key Science Project observation strategy and a source model incorporating both supernova remnant and pulsar wind nebula populations, as well as diffuse emission. Bottom: a zoom of an example 20° region in Galactic longitude [2].

While CTA is designed as a γ -ray observatory it will, as part of its normal operation, collect an enormous quantity of valuable information on charged cosmic rays. Of particular interest are the highest energy cosmic-ray electrons, which must be associated with nearby particle accelerators (which can therefore be studied using CTA data in both the γ -ray and electron channels), and heavy nuclei, which can be separated using their direct Cherenkov emission (i.e. from the primary cosmic ray, rather than from the secondary products in an air shower).

Both γ -ray and cosmic-ray observations with CTA rely on nanosecond-timescale cameras to detect Cherenkov light. Other uses for the very large optical-photon collection area of the CTA telescopes do exist. Observations of optical targets with CTA could include the use of intensity interferometry, to provide unprecedented angular resolution at blue wavelengths for bright sources.

3. Technical Overview

CTA will be an observatory with arrays of IACTs on two sites, aiming to:

- improve upon the sensitivity level of current instruments by an order of magnitude at 1 TeV,
- significantly boost detection area, and hence photon rate, providing access to the shortest timescale phenomena,
- substantially improve angular resolution and field of view and hence ability to image extended sources,
- provide energy coverage for photons from 20 GeV to at least 300 TeV, to give CTA reach to high redshifts and extreme accelerators,
- dramatically enhance surveying capability, monitoring capability, and flexibility of operation, allowing for simultaneous observations of objects in multiple fields,
- serve a wide user community, with provision of data products and tools suitable for non-expert users, and
- provide access to the entire sky, with sites in two hemispheres. CTA will be operated as an open, proposal-driven observatory for the first time in VHE astronomy. The observatory-mode operation of CTA is expected to significantly boost scientific output by engaging a research community much wider than the historical ground-based γ -ray astronomy community.

The very wide energy range covered by the southern CTA array necessitates the use of **three different telescope sizes**: referred to as Large-, Medium- and Small-Sized Telescopes (LSTs, MSTs and SSTs). The LSTs provide sensitivity at the lowest energies and SSTs at the highest. There are multiple strong motivations for the wide CTA energy range: the lowest energies provide access to the whole universe (avoiding significant γ – γ absorption on the extragalactic background light); the highest energies are needed to study the extreme accelerators which we know from direct cosmic-ray measurements are present in our galaxy; a wide energy range maximises the chances of serendipitous detection of new source classes with unknown spectral characteristics, for example in the search for dark matter with an unknown WIMP mass; a wide energy range is key for discrimination between scenarios and to identify

features. All objects which have been studied over a wide energy range with good signal to noise using current IACT arrays exhibit features in their γ -ray spectra. Conversely, the narrow energy range and lower signal to noise measurements more typical of current generation instruments invariably result in spectra which are consistent with power-law forms. In the north, where the inner regions of the Galaxy are not entirely visible, there will be a greater emphasis on extragalactic targets. Therefore, in the interest of optimisation of the observatory, the northern CTA array will be implemented with only LSTs and MSTs.

Access to the full sky is necessary as many of the phenomena to be studied by CTA are rare and individual objects can be very important. For example, the most promising galaxy cluster, the brightest starburst galaxy and the only known gravitationally-lensed TeV source are located in the north. The inner Galaxy and the Galactic Centre are key CTA targets and are located in the south. Full sky coverage ensures that extremely rare but critically important events (for example a Galactic supernova explosion, bright gravitational wave transient, or nearby γ -ray burst) will be accessible to CTA. Individual CTA telescopes will have Cherenkov cameras with wide field of view: $>4.5^\circ$ for the LSTs, $>7^\circ$ for the MSTs and $>8^\circ$ for the SSTs. The wide camera field serves a dual purpose: to provide contained shower images up to large impact distance (improving collection area and resolution) for on-axis γ -rays and to increase the γ -ray field of view of the system as a whole. This characteristic of CTA is critical for the observation of very extended objects and regions of diffuse emission, as well as for surveys. Furthermore, the wide field reduces systematic errors, with a uniform response over regions much larger than the point-spread-function size (not always the case for current generation instruments).

The CTA design (the “baseline”) is for 99 telescopes in the south (4 LSTs, 25 MSTs, 70 SSTs) and 19 in the north (4 LSTs, 15 MSTs). The large telescope number and individual-telescope wide fields of view result in a CTA collection area which is one or more orders of magnitude larger than current generation instruments at essentially all energies, with substantial benefits for imaging, spectroscopy and light-curve generation. Multi-square-kilometer collection area is essential at the highest energies, where there is essentially zero background even in long exposures and sensitivity is limited by the collection of sufficient signal photons. For very-short-timescale phenomena, CTA is background free over much of its energy range and the large collection area is the key performance driver.

For events incident in the central parts of the CTA arrays, the number of recorded shower images will be >10 for all but the lowest energies. These high image multiplicities, combined with the contained nature of events and image information superior to existing instruments, provide excellent energy and angular resolution. A precision approaching 1 arc-minute on individual photons will be obtained for the

upper end of the CTA energy range, the best resolution achieved anywhere above the X-ray domain.

Figure 3: Comparisons of the performance of CTA with selected existing γ -ray instruments. Top: differential energy flux sensitivities for CTA (south and north) for five standard deviation detections in five independent logarithmic bins per decade in energy. For the CTA sensitivities, additional criteria are applied to require at least ten detected γ -rays per energy bin and a signal/background ratio of at least 1/20. The curves for Fermi-LAT and HAWC are scaled by a factor of 1.2 to account for different energy binning. The curves shown give only an indicative comparison of the sensitivity of the different instruments, as the method of calculation and the criteria applied are different. In particular, the definition of the differential sensitivity for HAWC is rather different due to the lack of energy reconstruction for individual photons in the HAWC analysis from which this curve is taken [4]. Bottom: angular resolution expressed as the 68% containment radius of reconstructed γ -rays (the resolution for CTA-North is similar). These plots represent the understanding of the performance of CTA at the time of completion of this document; for the latest CTA performance plots, see <https://www.cta-observatory.org/science/cta-performance>.

The ability to rapidly respond to external alerts, and to rapidly issue its own alerts, is built into the CTA design. In particular, the LSTs, where the energy range covered provides access to essentially the whole universe, are optimised for rapid movement, with a goal slewing time of 20 s (minimum requirement 50 s) to anywhere in the observable sky. A real-time analysis pipeline will enable the identification of significant γ -ray activity in any part of the field of view and the issuing of alerts to other instruments within one minute.

The dramatic improvement in the point-source sensitivity of CTA with respect to current instruments is a consequence of the combination of improved background rejection power, increased collection area and improved angular resolution. The improved background rejection power is achieved primarily through high image multiplicity and is particularly important for the study of extended, low-surface brightness objects and for low-flux objects where deep exposures are required. Figure 3 compares the sensitivity and angular resolution of the CTA arrays to a selection of existing γ -ray detectors.

4. Technology Drivers

For 50 years, ground-based γ -ray telescopes have successfully used single, tessellated mirror-surface designs. Designs of this type have been prototyped for all three sizes of CTA telescope, including the first LST at the northern site on La Palma.

The evolving scientific needs of the field motivated a search for a new design that features both better angular resolution and a wider field of view (FoV). Better angular resolution translates directly into better sensitivity to point sources, which are generally studied in the regime limited by the background from charged cosmic rays. It also enables the mapping of spatially-extended sources in sharper detail, ultimately enabling improved morphological studies important to understanding the particle acceleration processes involved. A wider FoV also improves the efficiency of survey observations and the response to transient events that are not well localized. It increases the effective collection area of the telescope as well, by enabling the detection of showers at larger impact parameter and reducing the cases of large-image camera truncation.

The angular resolution of current IACT arrays is still far from the intrinsic limit of the technique that is determined by shower fluctuations. It can be substantially improved for large arrays of IACTs if the camera pixels can be reduced below the current size ($\sim 0.15^\circ$), and if the image quality of the telescope optical system can be correspondingly improved; the pixel size is matched to the optical point-spread function (PSF) for cost optimization. Ideally, the pixel resolution should match (or oversample) the transverse size of the central region of the cascade, typically spanning a few minutes of arc.

Improving the camera resolution while at the same time increasing its FoV is problematic for existing IACT designs. A telescope with prime-focus optics has chromatic aberrations which can be reduced only by increasing the focal length. This, in turn, increases the plate scale and therefore the physical size of the individual pixels of a given angular size in the camera. The resulting telescope's cost can then be dominated by expensive large-aperture photomultiplier tubes (PMTs). The ASTRI SST team, of which Brazil is also participating (see Section 5), has been pioneering a new design which overcomes these limitations by constructing a dual-mirror system [5]. This optical design, a Schwarzschild-Couder Telescope (SCT), largely cancels aberrations and demagnify the images. The same principle is being also used in the construction of an MST prototype by USA and other partners within the CTAC (the so called SCT).

5. Organization, Partnerships, and Current Status

The development of CTA is currently organized by the Cherenkov Telescope Array Observatory (CTAO) gGmbH, a German non-profit corporation having shareholders from 11 European nations. Brazil participates of the CTAO Council meetings as invited, having a FAPESP observer. The CTAO Council of shareholder representatives is the governing body of the organization.

The sites chosen for CTA are both within the grounds of existing observatories: the European Southern Observatory (ESO) at Paranal in Chile in the south and the Observatorio del Roque de los Muchachos (ORM) of the Instituto de Astrofísica de Canarias (IAC) on La Palma in Spain in the north. Agreements between CTAO and each observatory have been completed and signed.

The CTA Consortium (CTAC) is a scientific collaboration established in 2010 consisting of 1500 members from **31 nations**. The Brazilian members started in the CTA Consortium in 2010 with 3 members (E. M. de Gouveia Dal Pino, V. de Souza, and U. Barres de Almeida), and currently number ~60 (see Table 1 in attachment). The CTAC has been the main group driving the development of CTA, identifying the science goals and the designing the instrumentation needed to meet them. CTAC technical work packages have built and tested prototype CTA telescopes (see Sec. 4). CTAC Science working groups have elaborated and continue to develop the CTA science capabilities.

Brazilian scientists are active within CTAC, several having leadership roles, including the current Coordination of CTA Editorial Board - SAPO (Vitor de Souza from 2019 to 2020), and the coordination of the multi-wavelength task force (Ulisses Barres de Almeida, from 2019 to 2020). As stressed in Section 1, the Brazilian members of CTAC are organized in three parties: CTA-SSTs, CTA-MSTs, and CTA-Rio, which are coordinated by Elisabete M. de Gouveia Dal Pino (IAG-USP), Vitor de Souza (IFSC-USP), and Ulisses Barres de Almeida (CBPF), respectively. CTA-BR members are at the following institutions: USP, UNESP, UnicSul, UFABC, UniCamp, UFRJ, CBPF, UFSCar,

Universidade Federal do Parana (see Table 1 in attachment). Each of the parties above are contributing in instrumentation developments of the SSTs, MSTs and LSTs prototypes, respectively, as well as in the Science case of CTA.

In the framework of the FAPESP Thematic Project 13/10559-5, the SST-BR party of IAG-USP and associated partners has obtained funding to participate in the construction of the ASTRI (Astrofisica con Specchi a Tecnologia Replicante Italiana) SST prototype for CTA, and a MINI-ARRAY of ASTRI SSTs in partnership with the Italian team of the CTA, and South Africa. The SST-BR group is funding three of the nine MINI-ARRAY structures; South Africa part of one (1) of the structures; and Italy the remaining telescopes of the array. The total amount obtained from FAPESP for this thematic project is 12.200.000,00 Reais.

As described in Section 4, the ASTRI SST is an inovative dual-mirror telescope based on a modified Schwarzschild – Couder design for Imaging Atmospheric Cherenkov Telescopes (IACT). The telescope has a primary mirror diameter of 4.3 m, a primary-to-secondary distance of 3 m and a distance from the camera to the secondary mirror of 0.52 m. It adopts an altitude-azimuthal design in which the azimuth axis permits a rotation range of $\pm 270^\circ$. The mirror dish is mounted on the azimuth fork, which allows rotation around the elevation axis from -1° to $+90^\circ$. The mast structure that supports the secondary mirror and the camera is fixed on the mirror dish. The resulting mechanical structure has a weight of 16 tons but is also very stiff that in turns has proven advantageous (see [6] and references therein). Recently, the CTAO has chosen the ASTRI (among other 2 prototypes) to be the structure that will compose all the SST telescopes of the CTAO.

Two Brazilian engineers have been involved in the development of the ASTRI prototype as well as with the construction of the camera detector, and they must continue their activities in Italy for at least one year more, in order to participate of the final testing of the telescope with the camera, and acquire the entire knowhow for future manufacturing in Brazil of other SST telescopes for the CTA-South Array.

The Mini-Array of 9 ASTRI SSTs will be installed in Tenerife, Canarias, starting next year, and is intended to be a precursor for CTA, as it will be operative in 2022, well before the CTA (see WP of ASTRI MINI-ARRAY).

The Brazilian MST party led by IFSC-USP (with the FAPESP Thematic Project 15/15897-1 support) is helping in the construction of the support for the camera of the MSTs, with a total budget 1.8 M-REAIS.

The LST or Rio party in Brazil is led by CBPF and is helping with the development of small mechanical components for the LST, in partnership with Germany, Japan and Spain, with a budget of 100 K-REAIS.

For the construction and operation of the CTA Observatory, the formation of an European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC), headquartered in Bologna, Italy, has been proposed. The CTAO ERIC would replace the existing CTAO gGmbH and receive its assets. The first stage application for the ERIC has been submitted to the European Union, and a board of governmental representatives (BGR) is preparing the documents needed for the subsequent stages of the application. Brazil has an invited observer to the meetings of the BGR though not currently participating as a proposed member. Negotiations are in course in order to Brazil to formally join the ERIC, or otherwise participate as a partner either under the terms of the ERIC charter or through a bilateral agreement with the ERIC.

Brazilian participation in CTAO construction will be in the context of membership in CTAC and coordination with CTAO (either the gGmbH or the ERIC). It is envisaged that CTAO will be constructed by the receipt of in-kind contributions built by teams of CTAC members, together with cash contributions to CTAO for project staff and infrastructure construction at the observatories. As discussed in this document, Brazilian groups hope to make a substantial contribution to the completion specially of the SST arrays with the ASTRI structure, as well as of the MSTs and LSTs, in collaboration with international partners from CTAC.

6. Schedule

As discussed in the Introduction, CTA has been in development for some time and the concept was reviewed. In the Astro2010 decadal survey [7], one of the conclusions was: “Complex and high-cost facilities are essential to major progress in astronomy and astrophysics and typically involve collaboration of multiple nations and/or collaboration of federal and non-federal institutions. These partnerships bring great opportunities for pooling resources and expertise to fulfill scientific goals that are beyond the reach of any single country. However, they also present management challenges and require a new level of strategic planning to bring them to fruition.” The CTA project has been confronting these challenges while at the same time designing, building and evaluating prototypes of the candidate telescope designs.

It is planned to build CTA in two phases. Phase I consists of construction of the infrastructure for the full array and installation of a subset of telescopes to form partial arrays. Phase 2 consists of the operation of the Phase I arrays for science and the installation of the remaining telescopes to complete the arrays. The goal for Phase 1 is a “threshold implementation,” consisting of 15 MSTs and 50 SSTs in the south and 4 LSTs and 5 MSTs in the north. The ultimate scope of Phase 1 will depend upon the available funding.

Work on the infrastructure, including telescope foundations, is planned to begin at both sites in 2020. The southern site is within the ESO grounds but is a “green field”

requiring more development than La Palma. The first telescopes are expected to be accepted on site in 2020 in the north and in 2022 in the south. The completion of Phase 1 and start of Phase 2 is planned for the beginning of 2025.

A ten-year science program has been developed for CTA. It includes Key Science Programs, as discussed in Sec. 2, requiring somewhat less than half of the observing time over the ten-year period. The KSPs will be undertaken by the CTA Consortium. The balance of the observing time will be allocated to observers from nations supporting CTA construction and operations through a time allocation process administered by CTAO. Although it is envisaged that CTAO may have a useful life well beyond the initial ten years, a decision about continued operation (and continued Brazil participation) would be subject to review at a suitable time in the future.

7. Cost

CTA as a whole is a large, ground-based project. A cost estimate prepared by the CTAC for review by the CTA Science and Technical Advisory Committee (STAC) in 2015 and using 2015 costs obtained a total project cost of 400MEuro.

A key to accomplishing the impressive science that is possible with CTA is the completion of the SST array, which covers the extreme gamma-ray energy region >100 GeV–300 TeV. To this end, we seek construction support in Brazil sufficient to provide 10 to 15 SST structures to CTA. The current cost of ten such telescope structures would be \sim \$7.8MEuro.

The CTAO project office is currently updating the CTA costs in order to provide a cost book as part of the Stage 2 application for the CTAO ERIC. The revised cost book is not yet available. In the initial review, the revised costs are higher than previous estimates. In part, this is the result of a policy decision to incorporate the on-site installation and commissioning costs for each telescope into the telescope cost, since groups providing telescopes to the observatory will be expected to complete installation and commissioning prior to hand-off to CTAO.

Brazilian participation in supporting CTAO operations would be expected to be roughly in proportion to the fraction of CTAO construction funded by Brazil, at a level of \sim \$750 KEuro per year. Supporting CTAO construction and operations is critical for preserving CTA access for Brazilian scientists. As with the forthcoming very-high-energy γ -ray observatory ASTRI MINI-ARRAY (see Section 5; and WP of ASTRI Mini-Array), science with CTA data would be supported in Brazil by investigator-initiated proposals.

8. Summary

The current generation of IACT arrays, H.E.S.S., MAGIC, and VERITAS, have established the power of the atmospheric Cherenkov technique, increasing the number of known VHE γ -ray emitters twelvefold. The energy range covered by these observations, above ~ 100 GeV, is just above the prime energy coverage of Fermi-LAT and probes the most energetic particles produced in the most extreme environments in the Universe. CTA is designed to improve upon these current instruments in sensitivity by roughly an order of magnitude, as well as in angular resolution, field of view and energy coverage. Access to this large-scale ground-based capability for Brazilian scientists can be secured by Brazil investment at the mid-scale level.

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